

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346265450>

User relationship management in university libraries of Pakistan: Head librarians' perceptions

Article · May 2020

CITATIONS

0

READS

66

3 authors:

Mir Bahader

3 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Haroon Idrees

University of Sargodha

55 PUBLICATIONS 169 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Dr-Muhammad Asif Naveed

University of Sargodha

69 PUBLICATIONS 278 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Impact of Health Literacy on Fear of Covid-19, Protective Behavior, and Conspiracy Beliefs: University Students' Perspective [View project](#)

ECIL Conference [View project](#)

User Relationship Management in University Libraries of Pakistan: Head Librarians' Perceptions

**Mir Bahader
Haroon Idrees
Muhammad Asif Naveed**

Abstract

This study reports a part of results, from a PhD dissertation, about the perceptions of university library leaders about user relationship management (URM) in Pakistan. Survey method was employed using a web-based questionnaire. The data were collected from 190 heads/in-charge librarians from the universities/ degree awarding institutions. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied for data analysis using SPSS. The results revealed that the library leaders working at university libraries in Pakistan perceived user relationship management as important for attraction and retention of library users. There were no statistically significant differences in the perceptions of university librarians based on their gender. Conversely, age, academic qualification, and professional experience appeared to predict the perceptions of university librarians towards the importance of user relationship management. This study generated useful insights about the user relationship management as there were only few studies available on this area.

Keywords: Customer Relationship Management, Perceptions, Librarians, Relationship Marketing, Pakistan.

Introduction

Relationships are the main ingredients of life. It is hard to believe regarding any organization or society to stay alive without relationships. They are the invisible threads, which make a unique tie between the stakeholders and organizations. This bond, if strong, acts as a strong pillar, but if it is weak, it may get broken easily. Organizations understand the significance of the vital role played by relationships in achieving and maintaining competitive edge in the global market¹. The purpose of any business industry is to build relationships with customers, which gives an opportunity to the organization to serve them in the best way². The success of any organization is linked with keeping its customers intact by taking care of their benefits. Due to strong competitions in the market and other challenges of the modern times, companies are investing heavily on sustaining and developing strong relationships with their clients. Various modern and sensitive tools are in place to address the existing clients' needs as well as attract new prospective customers³.

The paradigm shifts from a push strategy to pull strategy of business and customer were considered the focal point of the business. In 1980s relationship marketing was came to light aiming to plan and promote customer loyalty, communication and long-term engagement. It is designed to develop strong relationships with customers by providing them with information directly suited to their needs and interests and by promoting open communication⁴. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) has emerged 1990's in the business world as a strategic solution to modern business problems. CRM has its roots in the age-old business philosophy which recognizes that customer centric business strategy should be implemented in the organization and all activities must be based on the customer preferences⁵. CRM is a philosophy, which places the customer at the center of the business processes, activities and cultures for improving customer satisfaction and maximizing profits. It helps in understanding customer preferences, like and dislike, and in building relationship with customers by providing the most suitable products and services with enhanced customer services. It integrates all subsystems to maintain a database of customer contacts, purchases, and technical support, among other things. This database helps the organization in identifying the desires and needs of the customers to improve the quality of the services and products and make a relationship strong and everlasting⁶.

Worldwide, service organizations are receiving much deserved attention to CRM, resulting from its predictable role in a country's economic development. These service sector organizations are mainly focusing on developing a strong relationship with the customers, because services are intangible goods that include attention, advice, experience, and discussion, etc. The scope of CRM in services sector organizations is enormous and it is believed that close contacts with stockholders are the objectives of their existence and make them faithful for their mutual benefits. In Pakistani scenario, various studies have been conducted on CRM that include: government organizations⁷, telecommunication sector⁸, health care/ hospitality, education⁹, banking¹⁰, insurance¹¹, legal consulting, news media, hotels¹², tourism, retail sales, airlines¹³, and libraries¹⁴. This implies that in Pakistan services sector a significant work has been conducted owing to its needs and importance.

Customer relationship management and libraries

Libraries are services-oriented organizations which plan to accomplish users' needs and preferences in an efficient and effective way. Academic libraries are an essential part of the university, administered to meet the information and research needs of its students, faculty, and staff. No one can deny from the fact that academic libraries play crucial role in learning, teaching, research, professional development and spreading of knowledge. For more than decades, academic libraries have been challenged and remained under pressure by the impact of the IT, World Wide Web, especially search engines, on users' preference for seeking information resources. The ubiquitous digital information environment of the Internet has changed library users in terms of their expectations and searching behavior¹⁵. Library users belong to different communities and their desires are different. The new users are picky, demanding, strongly aware, and in the driver's seat that they can see and control the situation¹⁶. It is apparent that there is a dire need of close contact between library and users to know the provided services and products are as per users' needs and requirements. In the present scenario library image is in decline. The customers are switching over frequently to avail the better facilities from other sources through internet. New and advanced services and products are being introduced continuously in the market. Thus, the academic libraries have to upgrade their products, perk up user services and create a relationship of trust through proper care of customer needs and regular communications. Apart from that, there is intense competition among the Private Sector Universities, Public Sector Universities and other types of universities and they are all taking steps to attract and retain the users.

There is a dire need to provide new technologies, new services and resources, research facilities, globalization of services and the concept of all the facilities under one roof leading to user delight and satisfaction. It will be possible only through execution of customer relationship management in academic libraries and will generate better results when they manage their customers in order to identify, satisfy and retain their most profitable users. This is a key objective of CRM strategies¹⁷. A good and strong relationship bond between library and users will encourage users to come and use library resources and the relations are valued as the interactive activities. Academic libraries have always been very dedicated to satisfy their user's needs and strive for their satisfaction up to the maximum, also considered how to manage and operate user services in an effective and efficient way. CRM highlights the customer-centric approach and makes strong relationship with users to conform to the user-focus on library business¹⁸. With the help of CRM, user's satisfaction, loyalty, retention, financial benefits and a good image of the academic libraries can be developed.

Customer relationship management is not a new notion for the libraries. This concept was introduced by prominent library scientist S.R Ranganathan¹⁹ in 1931. He produced five laws of Library & Information Science in which he used shop resemblance to sensitize the services with a business approach and called for libraries and information centers to accept that they are businesses, not just a source and storehouse of information. According to him, "As the reputation and fame of a shop rests very much on the resourcefulness, knowledge of the commodities in the shop and a sense of enthusiasm to be of service

to the customers of the shop on the part of shop assistants, the success of the library service very much depends on the head and the heart of the library staff". He says that a library user expects the same services as that of a customer. To him: "The library has now to develop the methods of a modern shop. It is true that, in a great many libraries, it may not be possible to have enough assistants just waiting around for someone to come in. We must keep a cheerful outlook and on no account show discourtesy. It's nice to know that the users love support and keep smiling"²⁰. These five laws have stressed on uniting the users with library products and services with the purpose to maximize the use of resources and serving them to their highest satisfaction and pleasure. The formal CRM strategy has been transmitted in the business world in the late 90s. Later on, and on the realization of its importance, the idea was conceived and sparingly put into practice by the libraries as well. However, the literature on Customer Relationship Management in the context of the Library and Information Science points towards the wider use of all library products and services under one roof leading to personal relationships and CRM concept.

Green²¹ have been addressed that library managers must be more than mere custodians of books and materials; they should be professors of the readers, advocate of the library products and services to the broader community, encouraging use of the library resources, creating a welcoming atmosphere, teaching clients how to use and evaluate resources, and communicate the significant and values of libraries to the community. The study of Keating and Hafner²² suggested the CRM business models that can be implemented in academic libraries and build up one-to-one relationship strategy that bequeath the libraries with capabilities to change methods, strategies, procedures and its role in educational and research. Seeman and O'Hara²³ viewed that the execution of CRM strategies in an academic setting can perk up user personal date and information, process management and increase students' satisfaction loyalty and retention. Wang²⁴ shares that by enforcing CRM policies; the lack of experience of libraries can be tackled. He further says that one of the greatest challenges is to develop understanding of CRM features, usage and its positive outcomes to the library staff.

A study was carried out by Umar²⁵ to examine the application of customer relationship management in selected university libraries in North Western States of Nigeria and concluded that current awareness services, information and referral service, Internet services and exhibition and displays were the major information services provided by the selected university libraries. It was revealed that personal contacts, complaint boxes, notice boards and news bulletin were the popular type of media used for communication with customers, and Inverters, TV, e-mail was only used in Kashim Ibrahim Library while mobile phone, website, webpage and telephone (landline) respectively were not used in the university libraries studied. It was found that there is no significant difference in the type of CRM strategies adopted by university libraries to determine their customer satisfaction. This study concludes that application of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) selected university libraries has significant influence on information service delivery. This study has been recommended the need for intensified efforts at attracting and retaining a customer base by university libraries through quality information service delivery, recruitment of qualified library staff, regular communications, regular evaluation of customers' needs and the use of short Message Service (SMS) facility.

The study of Siriprasoetsin, Tuamsuk, and Vongprasert²⁶ stated that most Thai academic libraries had no ways to develop and sustain contacts with clients. Although there were few CRM applications in some academic libraries such as a study of clients' behaviors and requirements, development of clients' history, and offering of many channels for clients' interaction, most of these applications were linked to the conventional library services such as distribution, library to library borrowing and services of current awareness. There were few novel practices concentrating on clients in Thai academic libraries. They further put forward following on the development and implementation of CRM in academic libraries: (1) CRM ought to be made part of the library strategic plan. (2) CRM must be of pivotal role in the development of library service quality. (3) Library administrators must have an effective leadership role to get the benefit of CRM practices in the library. (4) Library related staff must have a thorough

understanding of the importance and the link of CRM towards library service improvement. (5) The working cultures for CRM effectiveness, such as teamwork, cross functional work and quality communication among staff must be appreciated and followed in the library. (6) Technology must be fully backed up by CRM in the library. According to Jamali et al.² mass marketing that works well in commercial organizations does not have a solid bearing in public libraries as individual customers have their unique area of study and requirements. Hence the use of client focused marketing tools is suggested.

Bahader²⁸ found that the majority of the library staff in the university libraries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Islamabad was trying their best to fulfill information needs of every user. They were always showed welcoming behavior, trying to care, serve and help users regarding the proper use of library services. Library staff strives to increase library users' community, a well-wisher of the library. They are quite efficient in problem solving and giving priority to key users and also ensure the privacy of users' personal information. The study further concluded that major obstacles in the implementation of CRM strategies in the university libraries are, "library and information science curriculum", which does not cater CRM. Lack of financial resources, deficiency of library staff training, insufficient Information technology infrastructure in libraries, unawareness about CRM practices, mechanism and benefits in library stakeholders' and lack of top management interest and commitment are the major issues with CRM execution in the university libraries. Hemon et al.²⁹ concludes that it doesn't matter how much equipped is the library in terms of books, but the customers whose requirements are the libraries trying to accomplish. This shows the importance of relationship management in libraries.

Leligdon, Quinn, and Briggs³⁰ suggest taking libraries as business with visitors as a client allows us to incorporate policies and practices to meet users' satisfaction. Creating an all-embracing, inclusive strategy for developing lasting relationships can strengthen support for libraries with all concerned, which in turn can help in overcoming the issues like deficiencies of funds and other pressure on showing values. Implementing the CRM may necessitate a 180-angle shift for academic libraries; however, the concept stated here helps in improving the academic libraries by sharing the total values to all persons concerned. Edalatiyan, Sanatjoo and Nowkarizi³¹ study the human resource perspective on the strategy and implementation of CRM in Iranian university libraries. The results depicted that the degree of understanding of librarians with CRM is high and the need of implementing and using CRM is very reasonable. The study of Fouad and Al-Goblan³² point out towards lack of perception of the CRM concept to the staff involved in the study. The results stated that 99 % of the people involved in the study were in support of the need of CRM systems. The study also outlined that Egyptians and Saudi libraries have the conducive environment for implementing CRM systems.

Bahader et al.³³ study user relationship management (URM) in university libraries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Islamabad and concluded that library professionals consider that URM practices in the libraries are beneficial for the uplift of libraries products and services and performing quite a number of URM activities, but, the head librarians do not have a proper insight of URM philosophy and practice. They are trying to contact with the users' and arrange orientation programs for new members. "Presentation" in the libraries is the major practices to make new members familiar with library services and functions. Libraries are using different practices to keep themselves closer with their customers as it strengthens the relations between libraries and users. The highest used activity to motivate users is "appreciation letter", used by 31.4 %, which was very low. "Face to face" and "e-mail" tactics were used by majority of libraries for users' communication. The remaining channels (telephone calls, class orientation, through letters, broadcast) were not being used properly. The majority of libraries do not have a proper user feedback mechanism. They used "ask a librarian" and E-mail (40.0%) each, for feedback which is not encouraging. The remaining mechanism of feedback (suggestion/complaint box, survey, complaint register, help desk, orientation, discussion with user, and library webpage) was slightly used. "Meeting with the complainants" and "tries to fulfill user needs" are being used by a significant number of libraries in addressing users' complaints. It has also exhibited that there is no system of accountability

from top to bottom, everybody is relishing the swing of time and ignoring the fundamental morals of life. It is worth noting that this study used the term user relationship management rather than customer relationship management as in library environment user is widely used in the literature rather than customer. Therefore, the term user relationship management is the most appropriate term for investigating the customer relationship management.

An extensive review of published research revealed that no other study investigating user relationship management appeared, indicating the need for more inquiries on the proposed area. The current study was therefore planned to determine the perceptions of university library leaders toward user relationship management in Pakistan. The research questions included: (1) What are the perceptions of library leaders working in university libraries of Pakistan about different aspects of user relationship management? (2) Are there any significant differences in the perceptions of university library leaders based on their gender, age, academic qualification, and professional experiences?

Methods

A cross-sectional survey using a questionnaire was utilized to investigate the perceptions of university library leaders about user relationship management in Pakistan. The questionnaire containing 29 statements along with personal variables (e.g. age, gender, qualification and designation) was administered online among head/in-charge librarians working in universities and degree awarding institutions of Pakistan. The 29 statements related to perceptions were developed based on an extensive literature review which was submitted to a panel of 12 experts from the field of Library and Information Science for construct validity. A reliability analysis was executed on the perceived core value scale comprising 29 items. Cronbach's alpha showed the questionnaire to reach acceptable reliability, $\alpha = 0.97$.

Population: There were a list of 190 universities and degree awarding intuitions, both public and private, recognized in general and specialized categories available on the website of Higher Education Commission (HEC), Pakistan. HEC is a regulatory body of universities and degree awarding institutes in Pakistan. It was decided to conduct a census of all the head/in-charge librarians of the universities and degree awarding institutes recognized till December 2018 by HEC.

Data collection and analysis

The web-based questionnaire along with covering letter was administered through email among all the head/in charge librarians. A total of 140 questionnaires were completed by the survey participants. These questionnaires were screened for completeness and entered into SPSS for analysis. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. The frequencies and percentages along with mean scores and standard deviations (SD) were calculated separately for each statement to report the results. Moreover, Pearson correlation, an independent sample t-test and one-way ANOVA were also performed for relationship testing.

Results

Profile of the survey participants

Out of 140 total respondents, there were 112 males (80%) and 28 females (28%). A good number of respondents (n= 59, 42.1%) fall in the age group of 31-40 years which was followed by those having age group of 41-50 years (n= 48, 34.2%) and age group of 51-60 years (n= 21, 15.0%). Only nine (6.4%) respondents fall in the age up to 30 years and three (2.1%) respondents had age 60+ years. As far as the professional qualification is concerned, most of the participants, 82 (58.48%) had sixteen years of education BS/MLS/MLIS, which was followed by those having M Phil degree (n=51, 36.4%). Only Seven 7 (5%) respondents had PhD in Library and Information Science. Majority of respondents (n=66, 47.2%) had experience of more than 15 years which was followed by those having experience from 6-15 years (n= 56, 40%). There were only 18 (12.9 %) respondents who had professional experience less than five years.

Perceptions about the importance of user relationship management

The survey participants were asked to specify their perceived level of importance towards user relationship management (URM) in the library. Table 1 showed the participants responses. These participants perceived URM is very important in academic libraries as it helps to resolve users' complaints (Mean= 4.02, SD=.844), improve usage of library resource and services (Mean=3.99, SD=.898), improve service quality (Mean=3.98, SD=.917), address users' problems (Mean=3.95, SD=1.02), create user friendly environment (Mean=3.91, SD=.941), market library resources and services (Mean=3.89, SD=.953), strengthen users' satisfaction (Mean=3.88, SD=.993), enhance library image (Mean=3.86, SD=1.03), get users' feedback (Mean=3.83, SD=.936), advance information technology (Mean=3.82, SD=1.06), generate a conducive environment for learning (Mean=3.81, SD=.966), give honor to users' wants, needs and preferences (Mean=3.81, SD=.951), attract new users (Mean=3.81, SD=.944), adopt user-centered approach (Mean=3.76, SD=1.02), and improve efficiency, skills and worth of library employees (Mean=3.74, SD=.985).

These participants also perceived that URM enables library administration to orient new users (Mean=3.71, SD=1.01), ensure two-way communication (Mean=3.71, SD=.1.06), increase employee satisfaction (Mean=3.71, SD=.916), improve users' retention (Mean=3.66, SD=.903), develop need-based resources and services (Mean=3.64, SD=.990), sustain the long-term users' relationship (Mean=3.64, SD=.968), develop library community (Mean=3.61, SD=1.07), enrich mutual benefits of the library and its users (Mean=3.61, SD=1.00), develop users' loyalty (Mean=3.60, SD=.872), retain existing users (Mean=3.59, SD=.966), enhance user base (Mean=3.49, SD=.948), give users' potential for Life Time Value to library (Mean=3.49, SD=1.13), increment of valuable users (Mean=3.47, SD=.999) and approach users selective (Mean=3.36, SD=.858).

Table 1
Participants' perceptions about importance of User Relationship Management (N-140)

Rank	User Relationship Management is important in...	Not Imp.	Somewhat Imp.	Imp.	Very Imp.	Extremely Imp.	Mean	SD
		F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)		
1	Resolve users' complaints	2(1.4)	3(2.1)	27(19.3)	66(47.1)	42(30.0)	4.02	.844
2	Improvement of usage of library resources and services	2(1.4)	7(5.0)	24(17.1)	65(46.4)	42(30.0)	3.99	.898
3	Improvement of service quality	1(0.7)	8(5.7)	30(21.4)	55(39.3)	46(32.9)	3.98	.917
4	Address users' problems	4(2.9)	6(4.3)	34(24.3)	45(32.1)	51(36.4)	3.95	1.020
5	Creating a user-friendly environment	4(2.9)	4(2.9)	32(22.9)	60(42.9)	40(28.6)	3.91	.941
6	Marketing of library resources and services	2(1.4)	10(7.1)	30(21.4)	58(41.4)	40(28.6)	3.89	.953
7	Strengthening of users' satisfaction	2(1.4)	10(7.1)	36(25.7)	47(33.6)	45(32.1)	3.88	.993
8	Enhancement of the library image	4(2.9)	9(6.4)	34(24.3)	48(34.3)	45(32.1)	3.86	1.033
9	Getting users' feedback	2(1.4)	7(5.0)	42(30.0)	51(36.4)	38(27.1)	3.83	.936
10	Advancement of information technology	3(2.1)	11(7.9)	42(30.0)	36(25.7)	48(34.3)	3.82	1.061
11	Generating a conducive environment for learning in library	2(1.4)	11(7.9)	36(25.7)	54(38.6)	37(26.4)	3.81	.966
12	Give honor to users' wants, needs and preferences	2(1.4)	8(5.7)	43(30.7)	49(35.0)	38(27.1)	3.81	.951
13	Attraction of new users	4(2.9)	6(4.3)	36(25.7)	61(43.6)	33(23.6)	3.81	.944
14	Adoption of user-centered approach in library	4(2.9)	10(7.1)	38(27.1)	51(36.4)	37(26.4)	3.76	1.015
15	Improvement of efficiency, skills and worth of library employees	3(2.1)	11(7.9)	39(27.9)	53(37.9)	34(24.3)	3.74	.985
16	Orientation programs for the new users	6(4.3)	12(8.6)	33(23.6)	54(38.6)	35(25.0)	3.71	1.068
17	Enabling the users' two-way communication	4(2.9)	13(9.3)	42(30.0)	42(30.0)	39(27.9)	3.71	1.063
18	Order to increase employee satisfaction	4(2.9)	4(2.9)	48(34.3)	56(40.0)	28(20.0)	3.71	.916
19	Improvement of users' retention	0(0)	15(10.)	43(30.7)	56(40.0)	26(18.6)	3.66	.903
20	Design/development of users' needs-based resources and services	4(2.9)	12(8.6)	42(30.0)	54(38.6)	28(20.0)	3.64	.990
21	Sustaining the long-term users' relationship	4(2.9)	10(7.1)	45(32.1)	54(38.6)	27(19.3)	3.64	.968
22	Development of library community	4(2.9)	18(12.9)	40(28.6)	45(32.1)	33(23.6)	3.61	1.071
23	Enrichment of mutual benefits of library and its users	4(2.9)	14(10.0)	42(30.0)	53(37.9)	27(19.3)	3.61	1.001
24	Development of users' loyalty	2(1.4)	11(7.9)	47(33.6)	61(43.6)	19(13.6)	3.60	.872
25	Retaining of existing users	2(1.4)	15(10.7)	48(34.3)	48(34.3)	27(19.3)	3.59	.966
26	Enhancement of user base	4(2.9)	14(10.0)	51(36.4)	52(37.1)	19(13.6)	3.49	.948
27	Giving users' potential for Life Time Value to the library	8(5.7)	19(13.6)	39(27.9)	45(32.1)	29(20.7)	3.49	1.135
28	Increments of valuable users	4(2.9)	20(14.3)	42(30.0)	54(38.6)	20(14.3)	3.47	.999
29	User selective approach	2(1.4)	18(12.9)	58(41.4)	51(36.4)	11(7.9)	3.36	.858

Scale: 5=Extremely Important; 4=Very Important; 3= Important; 2=Somewhat Important; 1=Not important

Significance Testing

Gender and URM perceptions: A series of an independent sample t-test was performed to determine whether the male and female perceptions about each statement of user relationship management vary or not. The results indicated no statistically significant mean differences in the perceptions of university librarians about all the statements of user relationship management based on their gender as p-values were greater than the alpha value (0.05).

Age and URM perceptions: A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was computed to assess the relationship between URM perceptions and age while having age as an independent variable. Table 2 indicated no correlation between age and URM perception for most of the statements as p-values were greater than alpha values at 0.05 and 0.01. However, there was a significant but positive relationship between participants' URM perceptions based on age for the statement of "Retaining of existing users" ($P=0.029<0.05$), "Strengthening of users' satisfaction" ($P=.027<0.05$), "Development of users' loyalty" ($P=.045<0.05$), "Improvement of users' retention" ($P=.014<0.05$), "Getting users' feedback" ($P=.041<0.05$), "Address users' problems" ($P=0.046<0.05$), "Improvement of the services quality" ($P=.016<0.05$), "Give honor to users' wants, needs and preferences" ($P=.005<0.05$), "Creating user friendly environment" ($P=.013<0.05$), "Adoption of user-centered approach in library" ($P=.001<0.05$), "Creating conducive environment for learning in library" ($P=.026<0.05$), and "Enabling the users two way communication" ($P=.003<0.05$) respectively. In other words, the university library leaders having older ages perceived higher importance for these URM attributes.

Table 2

Correlation of Participants' Perceptions about User Relationship Management and Age -- (N-140)

SN	URM perception Attributes	Pearson correlation	Sig. (2- tailed)
1	User selective approach	.140	.100
2	Attraction of new users	.115	.174
3	Enhancement of user base	-.018	.831
4	Sustaining the long-term users' relationship	.097	.255
5	Increments of valuable users	.001	.992
6	Giving users' potential for Life Time Value to the library	-.100	.242
7	Order to increase employee satisfaction	.140	.099
8	Resolve users' complaints	.151	.076
9	Enhancement of the library image	-.029	.732
10	Development of library community	-.084	.324
11	Design/development of users' needs based resources and services	.019	.827
12	Enrichment of mutual benefits of library and its users	.094	.271
13	Advancement of information technology	.043	.616
14	Improvement of usage of library resources and services	.105	.217
15	Marketing of library resources and services	.036	.674
16	Orientation programs for the new users	-.001	.994
17	Improvement of efficiency, skills and worth of library employees	.075	.379
18	Retaining of existing users	.184	.029*
19	Strengthening of users' satisfaction	.187	.027*
20	Development of users' loyalty	.170	.045*
21	Improvement of users' retention	.207	.014*
22	Getting users' feedback	.173	.041*
23	Address users' problems	.169	.046*
24	Improvement of the service quality	.204	.016*

25	Give honor to users' wants, needs and preferences	.236	.005**
26	Creating a user-friendly environment	.210	.013*
27	Adoption of user-centered approach in library	.279	.001**
28	Creating a conducive environment for learning in libraries	.188	.026*
29	Enabling the user's two-way communication	.247	.003**
	Overall, URM perception	.143	.092

* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$

Academic qualification and URM perceptions: The one-way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was carried out to test differences in mean scores of participants' perception for user relationship management based on their academic qualification. The results indicated no relationship between participants' URM perceptions based on their academic qualification for most of the statements as p-values were greater than alpha values at 0.05. However, there was a significant statistical relationship between participants' URM perceptions for certain statements as p-values were smaller than alpha values at 0.05. Table 3 outlines such statements: "Enhancement of user base" ($F = 3.504$, $P = 0.017 < 0.05$), "Retaining of existing users" ($F = 2.889$, $P = 0.038 < 0.05$), "Sustaining the long-term users' relationship" ($F = 4.481$, $P = 0.005 < 0.05$), "Giving users' potential for Life Time Value to library" ($F = 3.226$, $P = 0.025 < 0.05$), "Strengthening of users' satisfaction" ($F = 3.085$, $P = 0.029 < 0.05$), "Address users' problems" ($F = 5.812$, $P = 0.001 < 0.05$), "Give honor to users' wants, needs and preferences" ($F = 3.520$, $P = 0.017 < 0.05$), "Creating user friendly environment" ($F = 4.761$, $P = 0.004 < 0.05$), "Adoption of user-centered approach in library" ($F = 4.761$, $P = 0.003 < 0.05$) and "Enabling the users two way communication" ($F = 3.484$, $P = 0.018 < 0.05$). Furthermore, a post hoc analysis using Tukey's HSD for pair wise comparisons showed that the participants having PhD and MPhil degrees perceived higher importance for the need of user relationship management as compared to those having BS/MLIS (16-year education).

Table 3

Participants' Mean Differences in URM perceptions based on Academic Qualification (N=140)

Serial No.	URM perception Attributes	Academic Qualification						F Value	Sig.
		BS/MLIS 82(58.48%)		M Phil 51(36.4%)		PhD 7(5.0%)			
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
20	Enhancement of user base	3.47	.98	3.45	.85	4.28	.48	3.50	.017*
21	Retaining of existing users	3.52	1.01	3.58	.85	4.57	.53	2.88	.038*
22	Sustaining the long-term users' relationship	3.58	.96	3.66	.90	4.57	.53	4.48	.005*
23	Giving users' potential for Life Time Value to library	3.28	1.16	3.68	1.1	4.42	.78	3.22	.025*
24	Strengthening of users' satisfaction	3.70	1.06	4.17	.86	4.00	.57	3.08	.029*
25	Address users' problems	3.86	.96	4.09	1.0	4.57	.53	5.81	.001*
26	Give honor to users' wants, needs and preferences	3.72	.92	3.96	.93	4.14	.69	3.52	.017*
27	Creating user friendly environment	3.81	.87	4.07	.97	4.42	.53	4.62	.004*
28	Adoption of user-centered approach in library	3.60	1.01	4.01	.92	4.28	.75	4.76	.003*
29	Enabling the user's two-way communication	3.53	1.03	3.92	1.1	4.42	.53	3.48	.018*

* $P < 0.05$

Professional experiences and URM perception: A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was applied to assess the relationship between participants' professional experiences and URM perceptions. Table 4 indicated no correlation between participants' professional experience and URM perception for the statements (serial number 1-14) as p-values were greater than alpha values at 0.05 and 0.01. However, there was a significant but positive relationship between participants' URM perceptions based on their professional experience for the statements from 15-29 which means that the participants having larger professional experience also had higher perceived importance for these URM attributes. The overall relationship between participants' perceptions about URM importance and professional experience exist, and the relationship is positive and partially strong.

Table 4

Correlation of Participants' Perceptions about User Relationship Management and Professional Experiences (N-140)

SN	URM perception Attributes	Pearson correlation	Sig. (2- tailed)
1	User selective approach	.145	.086
2	Enhancement of user base	.027	.754
3	Sustaining the long-term users' relationship	.071	.407
4	Increments of valuable users	.043	.610
5	Enhancement of users' potential in terms of their Life Time Value	.056	.512
6	Development of users' loyalty	.108	.204
7	Improvement of users' retention	.127	.134
8	Increments of employee's satisfaction	.079	.351
9	Enhancement of the library image	.091	.286
10	Development of library community	.015	.860
11	Advancement of information technology	.113	.184
12	Improvement of usage of library resources and services	.158	.062
13	Orientation programs for the new users	.046	.591
14	Improvement of efficiency, skills and worth of library employees	.095	.264
15	Attraction of new users	.181	.032*
16	Retaining of existing users	.223	.008**
17	Strengthening of users' satisfaction	.316	.000**
18	Getting users' feedback	.227	.007**
19	Resolve users' complaints	.213	.011**
20	Address users' problems	.242	.004**
21	Design/development of users' need based resources and services	.199	.019*
22	Enrichment of mutual benefits of library and its users	.168	.047*
23	Improvement of the services quality	.281	.001**
24	Marketing of library resources and services	.167	.048*
25	Give honour to users' wants, needs and preferences	.275	.001**
26	Generating user friendly environment	.247	.003**
27	Adoption of user-centered approach in library	.325	.000**
28	Generating conducive environment for learning in library	.182	.031*
29	Enabling the users two way communication	.276	.001**
	Overall, URM perception	.212	.012*

* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$

Discussion and Conclusions

A closure look at the results indicated that the library leaders working at university libraries of Pakistan perceived different attributes of user relationship management as important for both attraction of new users and retention of existing library users. These results tend to agree with those of Edalatiyan, Sanatjoo and Nowkarizi³⁴ studies who reported the level of familiarity of librarians with CRM is high and the necessity of establishing and using CRM is too moderate. But differ from the study of Fouad, & Al-Goblan³⁵ referred to the lack of clarity of the CRM concept to the employees of university libraries in Egypt and Saudi Arabia. It shows that library professionals in Pakistan and Iran are more dynamic and research oriented while in Egypt and Saudi Arabia they are still preschooler. The results also revealed that CRM perform crucial role in resolve users' complaints and problems, improvement of service quality, creating user friendly environment, marketing of library products and services, enhancement of the library image, getting users' feedback, in IT, creating conducive environment for learning, user centered approach, user communication, and user and employee satisfaction etc. Studies pointed out that service quality affects the degree of customer satisfaction³⁶ and the idea of customer satisfaction can be better understood by applying the concept of customer complaints management³⁷. It shows that with the passage of time need, worth, importance, and awareness level of CRM is increasing and organizations and its employees feel that CRM is the only way to stay alive in the age of information technology. CRM Studies have shown that the amalgamation of the new and potential user is much more difficult and expensive than maintaining the current user; therefore, in order to be more efficient and effective, libraries seek to promote and build strong, beneficial, deep, and long-term relationships with their users to improve image, products and services, user satisfaction and loyalty, and get mutual benefits for their survival³⁸. In this regard, a number of studies have been conducted on CRM in various organizations and libraries.

The crux of URM is to maintain strong, mutual and beneficial relationship with users. Academic libraries have been faced several challenges and one of them is to retain current and magnetize prospective users. URM play a very important role in libraries. It helps in resolve users' complaints, increase library usage, improve service quality, address users' problems, creating user friendly environment, library marketing, users' satisfaction, enhancement of library image, getting users' feedback, positive utilization of IT, creating encouraging atmosphere for learning, fulfilling user needs, attraction of new users, creating user centered approach, improving employee skills, user communications, improving user retention and loyalty, developing library community, retaining existing users etc. There is a significant difference between university library leaders' perceptions about URM importance in libraries and their personal and demographic variables such as age, academic qualification, and professional experience except of gender. This study produced useful and positive approach for libraries, especially those engaged in CRM practices. The findings could be used as a guide for library professional to create user friendly and user centered approach in the libraries. The study will also make a significant contribution to existing knowledge as there were a small number of studies which addressed librarians' perceptions regarding user relationship management.

References

1. Soosay, C. A., & Hyland, P. A decade of supply chain collaboration and directions for future research. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 20(6), 2015. P613-630.
2. Drucker, P. F *Concept of the Corporation*. Routledge. 2017.
3. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. *Marketing management 14th edition*. Prentice Hall. 2011.
4. Hollensen, S. *Marketing management: A relationship approach*. Pearson Education, 2010.
5. Chen, I. J., & Popovich, K. Understanding customer relationship management (CRM) People, process and technology. *Business process management journal*, 9(5), 2003, p672-688.
6. Baran, R. J., Galka, R. J., & Strunk, D. P. *Principles of customer relationship management*. Cengage Learning. 2008.

7. Soltani, Z. & Navimipour, N. J. Customer relationship management mechanisms: A systematic review of the state-of-the-art literature and recommendations for future research. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 61, 2016. p667-688.
8. Jahanzeb, S., Fatima, T., & Khan, M. B. An empirical analysis of customer loyalty in Pakistan's telecommunication industry. *Journal of Database Marketing & Customer Strategy Management*, 18(1), 2011. p5-15.
9. Kundi, G. M., Khan, M. S., Qureshi, Q., Khan, Y., & Akhtar, R. Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in higher education institutions. *Industrial Engineering Letters*, 4(3), 2014. p23-28.
10. Bhat, S. A., & Darzi, M. A. Customer relationship management: An approach to competitive advantage in the banking sector by exploring the mediational role of loyalty. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 34(3), 2016. p388-410.
11. Shafique, M. N., Ahmad, N., Abbass, H., & Manzoor, R. Strengthen outcomes of insurance agent: An exploratory study in Pakistan. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 42(2176), 2015. p1-8.
12. Mohammed, A. and Rashid, B. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) in Hotel Industry: A framework Proposal on the Relationship among CRM Dimensions, Marketing Capabilities, and Hotel Performance. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 2 (4), 2012. p220-230
13. Ali, F., Dey, B. L., & Filieri, R. An assessment of service quality and resulting customer satisfaction in Pakistan International Airlines: Findings from foreigners and overseas Pakistani customers. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 32(5), 2015. p486-502.
14. Bahader, M., Ali, J., Idrees, H., Ali, A., & Awan, R. User relationship management practices in the university libraries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Islamabad, *International Journal of Industrial Management*, vol.4, 2018.
15. Rajesh, S. Developing relationship marketing with customers: a Scandinavian perspective, *Library Management*, 24 (1/2), 2003. p34-43.
16. Jutla, D. Enabling and measuring electronic customer relationship management readiness, *Proceedings of the 34th Hawaii International Conference on Systems Sciences*, 2001, p1-10.
17. Francis, B. *Customer relationship management: Concepts and tool*, 2004.
18. Gupta, D. K., & Jambhekar, A. Developing a customer-focus approach to marketing of library and information services. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 22(3), 2002.
19. Ranganathan, S.R. Five laws of library science, 1931, URL: <https://www.librarianshipstudies.com/2017/09/five-laws-of-library-science.html> (access April 03, 2020)
20. Ranganathan, S.R. *Five Laws of Library Science*, second edition, Bombay, India: Asia Publishing House, 1957.
21. Green, S. S. Personal relations between librarians and readers. *Library journal*, 1(2), 1876, p74-81
22. Keating, J. J. & Hafner, A. W. Supporting individual library patrons with information technologies: emerging one-to-one library services on the college or university campus. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 28(6), 2002. p426-29.
23. Seeman, E. D., & O'Hara, M. Customer relationship management in higher education: Using information systems to improve the student-school relationship. *Campus-Wide Information Systems*, 23(1), 2006. p24-34.
24. Wang, M. Y. Introducing CRM into an academic library. *Library Management*, 28(6/7), 2007. p281-291
25. Umar, I. *Application of customer relationship management (crm) in information service delivery in university libraries in north Western States of Nigeria*, thesis. 2010.
26. Siriprasoetsin, P., Tuamsuk, K., & Vongprasert, C. Factors affecting customer relationship management practices in Thai academic libraries. *The international information & library review*, 43(4), 2011. p221-229.

27. Jamali, R., Moshabaki, A., Aramoon, H. & Alimohammadi, A. Customer relationship management in electronic environment, *The Electronic Library*, 31(1), 2011. p119-130.
28. Bahader, M. *Customer relationship management: a study of university libraries in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Islamabad*, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Thesis. 2014.
29. Hernon, P., Altman, E. and Dugan, R.E. *Assessing Service Quality: Satisfying the Expectations of Library Customers*, ALA, Chicago, IL. 2015.
30. Leligdon, L., Quinn, T., & Briggs, L. Strategic CRM: Improving the business of academic libraries. *College & Undergraduate Libraries*, 22(3-4), 2015. p247-260.
31. Edalatiyan, Z., Sanatjoo, A., & Nowkarizi, M. Review of Acquaintance and Necessity of Implementing Strategy of Customer Relationship Management from the Perspective of Human Resources of Academic Libraries in Iran. *Library and Information Science Research (LISRJ)*, 7(1), 2017. p239-256.
32. Fouad, N., & Al-Goblan, N. Using customer relationship management systems at university libraries: A comparative study between Saudi Arabia and Egypt. *IFLA journal*, 43(2), 2017. p158-170.
33. Bahader, M., 2018, Op. cit
34. Edalatiyan, Z., Sanatjoo, A., & Nowkarizi, M. 2017, Op. cit.
35. Fouad, N., & Al-Goblan, N., 2017, Op.cit.
36. Oluwunmi, A. O., Durodola, O. D., & Ajayi, C. A. Students' Perceived Quality of Library Facilities and Services in Nigerian Private Universities. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 4(5), 2016. p41-50.
37. Lin, C. C. Effects of customer complaint management on customer satisfaction: an example of hypermarket in Taiwan. *International Journal of Management Cases*, 10(4), 2008. p37-50.
38. Nikoo, H., & Morovati, Ali. The Effect of Customer Relationship Management on Organizational Performance Aspects (Case Study: 3 to 5 Star Hotels of Mashhad). *Tourism Management studies*, 12 (39), 2017.p27-48.

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

PAKISTAN

LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE JOURNAL

1. Higher Education Commission's Recognized Journal

ISSN: 0030-9956

URL: www.lpb-pak.com

Quarterly

Special Issue	ICEIL-II-2020 LIS -- Sargodha University Conference	
Founder Patron <i>M. Adil Usmani (Late)</i> ***	CONTENTS	
Chief Editor <i>Dr. G.A. Sabzwari</i> ***	<i>Editorial (Guest) 2nd International Conference on Emerging Issues of Information Landscape (ICEIL-II) -2020</i> Dr. Haroon Idrees	3
Deputy Chief Editors <i>Prof. M. Wasil Usmani</i> <i>Prof. Dr. Nasim Fatima</i> ***	<i>Exploring personality traits and vocational interests in librarianship</i> Arif Khan, Sidra Mushtaq	6
Editors: <i>Abdul Oudoos</i> <i>Amna Khatoon, Dr.</i> <i>Azra Qureshi</i> <i>Nasreen Shagufta, Dr.</i> <i>Naushad Sabzwari</i> <i>Syed Ahmad Naqvi</i> <i>Zain Siddiqui</i> ***	<i>Investigating Job Satisfaction among Informational Professionals working at the University Libraries of Pakistan</i> Muhammad Ahmad Shah, Haroon Idrees, Muhammad Asif Naveed	17
Media Coordinators <i>Syed Khalid Mahmood</i> <i>Fareed Sabzwari USA</i> <i>Nadeem Sabzwari</i> <i>Canada</i> <i>Faheem Sabzwari USA</i> ***	<i>Relationship Between Job Characteristics And Job Satisfaction: A Systematic Review</i> Imtiaz Ahmad Khalil, Dr. Shamshad Ahmad	31
Secretary Management <i>Prof. Liaquat Ali Khan</i> <i>Sofia Liaquat</i>	<i>Status of Resources and Services in the Public Libraries of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: A Study</i> Mohammad Hussain, Haroon Idrees	48
	<i>Research Support Resources and Services in University Libraries of Pakistan: A Situational Analysis</i> Nusrat Ali, Muhammad Asif Naveed	57
	<i>Disaster Preparedness at University Libraries in Punjab, Pakistan: Role and Challenges</i> Ghulam Mustafa, Haroon Idrees	64
	<i>Relationship of Emotional Intelligence with Information Seeking Anxiety among Postgraduate Students at Universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan</i> Rahim Jan, Shamshad Ahmed, Muhammad Asif Naveed	74
	<i>User Relationship Management in University Libraries of Pakistan: Head Librarians' Perceptions</i> Mir Bahader, Haroon Idrees, Muhammad Asif Naveed	85
	<i>Mapping the Scales Measuring Quality of Services in University Libraries: A Systematic Review</i> Habib.ur.Rehman, Haroon Idrees, Muhammad Asif Naveed	99
	<i>A study on information literacy instruction and its integration into curriculum in university libraries of Pakistan</i> Sohail Iqbal, Haroon Idrees	109
	<i>Impact of HEC Electronic Information Resources on Research Productivity of Academicians: A Systematic Review</i> Tahir Jan, Haroon Idrees, Muhammad Asif Naveed	118
	<i>Relationship of Soft Skills with Service Quality of Information Professionals at the University of the Punjab, Lahore</i> Qurat-ul-Ain, Waqar Ahmad Awan, Muhammad Asif Naveed	128
	<i>Knowledge Sharing Behavior of University Librarians in Punjab, Pakistan</i> Fakhra Naseem, Ghulam Murtaza Rafique, Haroon Idrees	138
	<i>Non-Use of Academic Library: A Case of University of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan</i> Sajjad Ahmad, Waqas Gul	148
	<i>Information Accessibility for Coal Mine Workers</i> Asif Ali, Muhammad Asif Naveed	157
	<i>Building a Successful Liaison Librarians Program: The Case of Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University, Saudi Arabia</i> Shafiq Ur Rehman, Murtaza Ashiq	163

PLISJ is a quarterly journal of Library Promotion Bureau.

Views expressed are not necessarily of the journal's publishers.

All Correspondence should be addressed to:

The Chief Editor, P.O. Box 8421, Karachi University Campus, Karachi.

Phone: 0364-201-8823 Email: lpb_pakistan_66@yahoo.com

Contributors of this special Issue

<p>Dr. Haroon Idrees Chairman, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan haroon.idrees@uos.edu.pk</p>	<p>Mir Bahader PhD Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan mirbahaderkttk@yahoo.com</p>
<p>Arif Khan PhD Scholar Charles sturt University, Canberra, Australia / PARD, Peshawar arifpard@gmail.com</p>	<p>Habib.ur.Rehman PhD Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan habib.uop@gmail.com</p>
<p>Sidra Mushtaq Visiting Lecturer, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan sidrawan786@gmail.com</p>	<p>Sohail Iqbal PhD Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan sohailawans@yahoo.com</p>
<p>Muhammad Ahmad Shah PhD Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan ahmadshahge@gmail.com</p>	<p>Tahir Jan PhD Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan tahirjan@uop.edu.pk</p>
<p>Dr. Muhammad Asif Naveed Assistant Professor, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan asif.naveed@uos.edu.pk</p>	<p>Qurat-ul-Ain M. Phil. Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan quratulain.aziz92@gmail.com</p>
<p>Dr. Shamshad Ahmad Associate Professor, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan shamshad.ahmed@uos.edu.pk</p>	<p>Fakhra Naseem M. Phil. Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan fakhrakhalid033@gmail.com</p>
<p>Imtiaz Ahmad Khalil PhD Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan imtiazahmadkhalil@gmail.com</p>	<p>Dr. Sajjad Ahmad Assistant Professor, Department of Library and Information Science, University of Peshawar</p>
<p>Mohammad Hussain PhD Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan mhustb@gmail.com</p>	<p>Waqas Gul Librarian, Hamza Army Public school and College, Rawalpindi gulwaqas9696@gmail.com</p>
<p>Nusrat Ali <i>Librarian, Quaid-e-Azam Library, University of Gujrat, Gujrat</i> nusrat.ali@uog.edu.pk</p>	<p>Asif Ali M. Phil. Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan</p>
<p>Ghulam Mustafa PhD Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan ghulam.mustafa@uos.edu.pk</p>	<p>Dr. Shafiq Ur Rehman Associate Professor, Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University, Dammam suRehman@iau.edu.sa</p>
<p>Rahim Jan PhD Scholar, Department of Library & Information Sciences, University of Sargodha, Sargodha, Pakistan rahimjanrajjar@gmail.com</p>	<p>Murtaza Ashiq Librarian, Islamabad Model College for Boys gmurtazaashiq00@gmail.com</p>